

Cilosari: a new rice variety released in Indonesia through cross hybridization of the mutant line with IR36

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We irradiated seeds of variety Seratus Malam with different doses of gamma rays (10, 20, 30, and 40 krad) in 1983. The M₂ generation plants were selected for semidwarf stature, and from 50,000 M₂ plants, 130 semidwarf mutants were

selected. A semidwarf mutant, SM-268 /PsJ, selected from the 20-krad treatment, was used for analysis of allelic relationship. In the allelic test, semidwarf mutant SM-268/PsJ was crossed with IR36. However, in the F₃ an early maturity line Obs-1647/PsJ was selected and tested for yield potential in the F₁₀ generation. The agronomic characters of Obs-1647/PsJ and the mother varieties are in Table 1.

Based on yield trials at 27 locations during 1992-95, Obs-1647/PsJ showed a higher yield potential at several loca-

tions when compared with IR64 (Table 2). The Ministry of Agriculture in Indonesia released this line in July 1996 as Cilosari, a variety for irrigated areas. ■

Table 1. Agronomic characters of Obs-1647/PsJ (Cilosari) and mother varieties IR36 and SM-268/PsJ.

Character	Parent 1 SM-268/PsJ (mutant)	Parent 2 IR36	Derived line Obs1647/PsJ (Cilosari)
Plant height (cm)	60-65	70-80	110-125
Maturity (d)	110-115	110-120	110-120
Productive tillers (no.)	5-7	14-19	10-15
1,000 grain weight (g)	15-17	23-25	26-27
Amylose content (%)	22-23	24-25	20.5-21.0
Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	2.0-2.5	4.0-4.5	5.0-6.5
Cooking and eating quality	Not good	Medium	Good
Resistance to BPH biotypes 1 and 2	Susceptible	Resistant	Resistant
Resistant to bacterial leaf blight	Susceptible	Resistant	Resistant

Table 2. Mean yield of Cilosari in yield trials at 27 locations. 1992-95.^a

Location	1992-93 wet season		1993 dry season		1993-94 wet season		1994-95 wet season	
	Cilosari	IR64	Cilosari	IR64	Cilosari	IR64	Cilosari	IR64
Madiun	5.70 a	5.20 a	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lamongan	5.23 a	5.17 a	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ponorogo	8.40 a	8.30 a	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bekasi	7.30 a	5.90 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
Tulungagung	8.10 a	7.80 a	-	-	-	-	-	-
Probolinggo	7.10 a	5.60 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
West Sumatera	4.90 a	6.40 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
Yogyakarta	-	-	5.99 a	4.37 a	-	-	-	-
Banyuwangi	-	-	4.58 a	4.20 a	-	-	-	-
Jombang	-	-	5.01 a	5.33 a	-	-	-	-
Ponorogo	-	-	5.45 a	5.94 a	-	-	-	-
Serang	-	-	3.69 a	3.63 a	-	-	-	-
Temanggung	-	-	4.92 a	5.38 a	-	-	-	-
Ogankomering	-	-	-	-	6.47 a	6.43 a	-	-
North Aceh	-	-	-	-	6.55 a	5.73 a	-	-
Central Lampung	-	-	-	-	8.46 a	8.02 a	-	-
Bandung	-	-	-	-	10.14 a	9.68 a	-	-
South Sulawesi	-	-	-	-	5.82 a	5.07 a	-	-
South Lampung	-	-	-	-	7.04 a	5.50 b	-	-
Bandung	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.97 a	9.68 a
West Aceh	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.63 a	2.65 b
Indragiri Hilir	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.71 a	2.42 b
Tanjung Jabung	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.65 a	4.45 b
Kerinci	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.83 a	5.67 b
Bengkalis	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.76 a	2.55 b

^aIn a row in the same location, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by HSD test at the 5% level.

FARO 44 and FARO 50: two irrigated lowland rice varieties for Nigeria

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Irrigated lowland rice is grown on around 10% of the 1.77 million ha planted to rice in Nigeria. In August 1996, the National Crop Variety Release Committee in Nigeria released two semidwarf varieties, FARO 44 and FARO 50, for this ecosystem. They are suitable for all the zones except southeastern Nigeria, where African rice gall midge (ARGM) is a major problem. Their detailed characteristics are shown in the table.

FARO 44 is the varietal name given to the line SI-692033. It was bred at Chiayi Agricultural Experiment

Agronomic characteristics of two lowland rice varieties.

Characteristic	FARO 44	FARO 55
Designation	Sipi 692033	ITA230
Cross	Sipi 661044/ Sipi 651020	BG90-2 ⁴ / Tetep
Days to 50% flowering	85	90
Plant height (cm)	105	110
Blast resistance ^a	3	1
ARGM ^a	9	9
RYMV ^a	9	9
Iron toxicity ^a	7	7
Leaf scald ^a	3	1
Brown rice length (mm)	6.9	7.3
Brown rice width (mm)	2.2	2.2
L/W	3.1	3.3
Grain type	Long slender	Long slender
Chalkiness ^a	0	5
Gel temperature ^a	7	5
Amylose %	26.0	28.0
Husk color	Straw	Straw
1000-grain weight (g)	26.5	23.6
Av yield (t ha ⁻¹)	4.0	5.0
Yield potential (t ha ⁻¹)	8.0	10.0

^aSES scale, IIRI (1996).

Station, Kaohsiung, Taiwan, introduced through International Rice Testing Program nurseries in 1981, and further evaluated by the International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice-Africa and in multilocal coordinated rice evaluation trials (CRET) in Nigeria. After 3 yr in CRET, the line was further evaluated in farmers' fields by the National Ac-

celerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP).

FARO 50 is a varietal name given to line ITA230. It was selected from the F₄ lines introduced from the Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical, Colombia. As line 6902, it was selected for yield potential and blast resistance at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Ibadan. The line was

evaluated in CRET and NAFPP prior to its release.

Both FARO 44 and FARO 50 are resistant to leaf blast and leaf scald, but are susceptible to iron toxicity, ARGM, and rice yellow mottle virus. They have long, slender grains and high amylose content. Both are popular in irrigated rice areas of north and central zones of Nigeria. ■

Xingxiangyou 77, a high-yielding and fine-quality semi-aromatic hybrid rice

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Xingxiangyou 77 was developed at HHRRC using aromatic cytoplasmic male sterile line Xiangxiang A and nonaromatic restorer line Minghui 77. It was extensively tested and approved for release to farmers by the Hunan Provincial Crop Variety Release Committee in February 1997. Xiangxiang A, improved from the first aromatic CMS line Xiangxiang 2A, is another aromatic

CMS line developed by HHRRC. The new line has stable male sterility and better outcrossing characteristics than Xiangxiang 2A. Minghui 77, developed by the Sanming Agricultural Institute, Fujian, China, is a popular strong restorer line with good grain quality. The cross between these two parents was first made in 1993. In 1994, the hybrid was tested in the Hunan Rice Variety Multilocal Trial and yielded 6.9 t ha⁻¹ on average at all five locations, 5.5% higher (significant at 5% level) than check Weiyou 64. In the same year, it gave a mean yield of 5.9 t ha⁻¹ at six locations in the trial of new commercial fine-quality rice varieties of Hunan Province with a yield advan-

tage of 2.9% over check Xiangwanxian 1. Tested in the Hunan Rice Variety Regional Trials of 1995 and 1996, it gave a mean grain yield of 6.8 t ha⁻¹ over 14 and 12 locations, respectively, with yields of 2.3% and 5.6% higher than those of check Weiyou 64 (Table 1). In the on-farm trials and demonstration plots, it generally yielded 6.8 to 7.7 t ha⁻¹ when grown as late rice in a double-cropping system.

Most of the variety's grain quality characters met the 2nd class standards of fine-quality rice issued by the Chinese Ministry of Agriculture (Table 2). Furthermore, because its CMS line Xingxiang A is aromatic and its restorer line Minghui 77 is nonaromatic,

Table 1. Agronomic characters of Xingxiangyou 77. Hunan Rice Variety Regional Trial, China.

Hybrid	Year	Locations (no.)	Hybrids tested (no.)	Maturity (d)	Plant height (cm)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Filled spikelets (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield ^a (t ha ⁻¹)
Xingxiangyou 77	1995	14	10	114.0	99.1	108.7	69.2	27.4	6.8 ns
	1996	12	11	114.8	96.0	105.6	77.8	28.3	6.9 ns
Weiyou 64 (check)	1995	14	10	114.0	97.0	98.0	72.2	28.5	6.6
	1996	12	11	113.3	91.0	100.7	74.9	29.3	6.5

^ans = yields not significant by Duncan's SSR test (in 1995) or by Fisher's PLSD test (in 1996). The experiment used three replications.

Table 2. Grain quality performance of Xingxiangyou 77.

Hybrid/standard	Institutes ^a doing the testing (year)	Brown rice (%)	Milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Kernel		Chalky		Gelatinization temperature (alkali value)	Gel consistency (mm)	Amylose content (%)	Protein content (%)
					Length (mm)	L/W	Rice (%)	Area (%)				
Xingxiangyou 77	CNRRRI (1995)	81.6	73.6	58.4	7.1	3.1	46	50	6.8	62	24.0	12.2
	HRRI (1995)	81.0	77.5	56.0	7.2	3.1	61	26				
	HRRI (1996)	81.0	66.8	61.0	7.1	3.0	58	26				
CMA standard	1st class	>81	>74	>59	6.5-7.5	>3.0	<5	<5	>4	>60	17-22	>8
	2nd class	>79	>72	>54	5.6-6.5	2.5-3.0	<10	<10	>4	41-60	<25	>8

^a CNRRRI: Chinese National Rice Research Institute; HRRI: Hunan Rice Research Institute; CMA: Chinese Ministry of Agriculture.